

Introducing Algebraic Materials to Elementary School Students

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Abstract:

This article talks about the algebraic materials taught in elementary grades, what the elementary school teacher should know and be able to do during teaching them, and the tasks of teaching algebraic materials.

Keywords: algebraic material, arithmetic material, mathematical expression, task, numerical expression, elementary school, student, teacher.

In the primary grade mathematics program, it is established that algebraic materials are studied in an organic connection with arithmetic materials. The following algebraic concepts are taught to primary school students:

- Expression;
- Numerical expression;
- Variable expression;
- Equality;
- Numerical equality;
- Equation;
- Inequality;
- Numerical inequality;
- Variable inequality.

These concepts are the basis for in-depth study of many mathematical concepts and generalization of rules.

Algebraic material is taught in four academic years of primary education. Algebraic materials are also used in the teaching of each arithmetical material. It is necessary for students to consciously master the concept of each studied algebraic material. Algebraic materials taught in primary grades are the main foundation for algebra in higher grades.

When teaching algebraic materials, a primary school teacher should know the following:

- Learning materials with algebraic content in primary grade mathematics, their sequence in the curriculum by classes;
- Learned arithmetic in the process of introduction to algebraic materials
- content of materials;
- User manuals;
- Types of learning assignments in algebraic content;
- Used didactic games;
- Different methods, forms and methods of checking whether the algebraic material has been studied.

A primary school teacher should be able to do the following when teaching algebraic materials:

- To be able to apply arithmetical material and algebraic material and organic connection in practice;
- Being able to use instructional tools according to the purpose;
- Being able to use didactic games according to the purpose;
- Being able to practically apply various forms and methods of testing the student's knowledge;
- Be able to select written assignments that cover the elements of algebra.

There are the following tasks of teaching algebraic materials in elementary grades:

- Forming the skills of reading, writing and comparing numerical expressions in primary school students;
- Formation of calculation skills in students following the sequence of performing the actions in the expression;
- To train students to read and write letter expressions in the form of $b+a$, $c-d$, $8*a$, $d:2$, $c*b$, $a:b$ and substitute the given values of the letters and find the value of the expression teach to find.
- To introduce elementary school students to simple equations. It is a choice of equations, learning to solve them based on the connections between the components of the action and the result. The skills of teaching how to solve complex equations and solve problems using equations are formed.

A mathematical expression is a sequence of mathematical symbols that define numbers and operations on them, formed according to certain rules.

Introducing students to numerical expressions is carried out in the following 4 stages:

Stage 1. At the beginning of the 1st grade, students begin to read the following expressions: "If we add one to six, we get seven", "If we subtract two from five, three will come out".

Stage 2. At this stage, familiarization with mathematical expressions often involves expressions such as stage 1 operations ($5+3-2$, $2+2+2\dots$) and expressions called stage 2 operations ($6:2*2$, $4*3:2$) is typical.

Stage 3. Expressions at this stage include all four actions.

Step 4. At this stage, parenthetical expressions are introduced.

So, in elementary mathematics, algebraic materials are taught in connection with arithmetical materials. Nine algebraic materials are taught to elementary school students for 4 years.

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